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Synergies between a U.S.-based Electron-Ion Collider and European Research in Particle Physics

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Abstract

This document is submitted as input to the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU). The U.S.-based Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) aims at understanding how the complex dynamics of confined quarks and gluons makes up nucleons, nuclei and all visible matter, and determines their macroscopic properties. In April 2024, the EIC project received approval for critical-decision 3A (CD-3A) allowing for Long-Lead Procurement, bringing its realization another step closer. The ePIC Collaboration was established in July 2022 around the realization of a general purpose detector at the EIC. The EIC is based in U.S.A. but is characterized as a genuine international project. In fact, a large group of European scientists is already involved in the EIC community: currently, about a quarter of the EIC User Group (consisting of over 1500 scientists) and 29% of the ePIC Collaboration (consisting of ~ 1000 members) is based in Europe. This European involvement is not only an important driver of the EIC, but can also be beneficial to a number of related ongoing and planned particle physics experiments at CERN. In this document, the connections between the scientific questions addressed at CERN and at the EIC are outlined. The aim is to highlight how the many synergies between the CERN Particle Physics research and the EIC project will foster progress at the forefront of collider physics.

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1 Introduction

The Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) is a major new research facility to discover and understand the emergent phenomena of Quantum Chromo-Dynamics (QCD). Since 1999, there have been many dedicated scientific meetings to shape the physics case for the EIC, most notably the yearly POETIC meetings. In 2010 there was a ten-week program at the Institute of Nuclear Theory (INT) in Seattle that resulted in a 547-page document [1] detailing the science case. This was updated and condensed in the EIC white paper [2]. The U.S. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NAS) [3] report summarizes the physics objectives as follows: “An EIC can uniquely address three profound questions about nucleons - neutrons and protons - and how they are assembled to form the nuclei of atoms:

- How does the mass of the nucleon arise?
- How does the spin of the nucleon arise?
- What are the emergent properties of dense systems of gluons?”

To answer these fundamental questions one needs to probe with high resolution and high energy the quark and gluon structure of nucleons and nuclei. It is of great advantage to do this with a simple and well-known probe, such as the electron or the photon. The quark and gluon structure of nucleons is expressed theoretically in terms of parton distributions of various levels of detail and sophistication. For inclusive electron-proton or electron-ion Deep Inelastic Scattering (DIS), where one ignores details of the final state, the scattering process is described in terms of collinear (i.e., transverse-momentum integrated) Parton Distribution Functions (PDFs). When more aspects of the final state are measured, one can become sensitive to the three-dimensional momentum distributions (Transverse Momentum Dependent PDFs or TMDs). Exclusive and diffractive processes allow one to probe also transverse spatial distributions, given in terms of Generalized Parton Distributions (GPDs). The information contained in TMDs and GPDs is truly complementary since the position of partons in a transverse plane is not Fourier conjugate to their transverse momentum. Hence, the combined investigation of PDFs, TMDs, and GPDs, will allow one to arrive at a more complete picture of how nucleons are composed at the level of quarks and gluons. These studies go far beyond global (and scale-dependent) observations like “50% of the proton’s momentum is carried by gluons” or “no more than about 30% of the proton’s spin is carried by quarks” (a well-known conclusion from the EMC, SMC, and later experiments). More specifically, the three major themes of the EIC physics program that support the NAS physics objectives are:

- the flavor and spin structure of the proton
- three-dimensional structure of nucleons and nuclei in momentum and configuration space
- QCD in nuclei

Figure 1: Left and center: the (x, Q^2) phase space coverage of unpolarized and polarized electron-proton DIS for the EIC, in comparison with DIS and heavy-ion data from past and current facilities (updated version of Ref. [2]). Right: the (x, Q^2) phase space coverage for nuclei, compared to data from existing nuclear DIS experiments.

The EIC is a machine that is unique compared to any previous collider because of the combined availability of high energy, high luminosity, ion versatility, and polarization. It is the first ever machine with the capability

83 to collide highly polarized electrons on polarized protons and light ions, as well as on unpolarized heavier ions up
84 to uranium. The EIC has a large reach in x and Q^2 (see Fig. 1). High energy scattering of polarized electrons
85 and ions, including both longitudinally and transversely polarized light ions, is crucial to a full understanding
86 of the quark-gluon structure and dynamics of baryons, mesons, and nuclei. Compared to the HERA collider at
87 DESY, the EIC will have lower energy but a luminosity up to a thousand times higher, enabling measurements
88 that have never been feasible before. The NAS committee found the scientific case for EIC compelling, unique,
89 and timely. According to the NAS report [3]: *“The science questions that an EIC will answer are central to
90 completing an understanding of atoms as well as being integral to the agenda of nuclear physics today. In addition,
91 the development of an EIC would advance accelerator science and technology in nuclear science; it would as well
92 benefit other fields of accelerator-based science and society, from medicine through materials science to elementary
93 particle physics.”*

94 In addition, the high luminosity and cleaner environment (with respect to hadron colliders) will enable precision
95 studies in electroweak physics and some specific searches of physics beyond the Standard Model.

96 The fast-growing worldwide community of scientists interested in the EIC organized itself under the EIC Users
97 Group (EICUG) [web site <http://www.eicug.org/>]. As of February 2025, the EICUG consists of 1549 scientists
98 (including 377 theorists) from 303 institutions of 40 countries in all world regions, with a large European involvement
99 consisting of 412 scientists (27%) from 86 institutions.

100 In December 2019, following the extremely positive NAS assessment [3], the US Department of Energy (DoE)
101 established EIC Critical Decision 0 (CD-0), a “mission need” declaration, formally starting the EIC Project.
102 Following a call for detector proposals, the ePIC Collaboration was established in July 2022 with the goal of
103 realizing a general purpose detector designed to deliver the full EIC science program. As of February 2025, the
104 ePIC collaboration consists of 1000 members, of whom 29% are based in Europe. In April 2024, the EIC Project
105 received approval for Critical Decision 3A (CD-3A) which allows the EIC project to initiate long lead procurements.

106 With this document we highlight the elements of the EIC scientific program that will directly or indirectly impact
107 particle physics. In particular, we want to outline to the Panel of the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update
108 (ESPPU) the benefits that will be obtained in combining data from the EIC and CERN experiments. Moreover, this
109 research activity benefits greatly from the significant European involvement in the EICUG and ePIC collaboration
110 as highlighted above. We believe that such cross-cutting collaboration is central to the scientific progress in our
111 field and should be strongly encouraged.

112 The general need for and uses of high-energy electron-proton and electron-ion DIS are outlined in a separate
113 document submitted to this Panel [4]. Furthermore, detailed aspects of the R&D programs of both the U.S.-based
114 EIC accelerator [5] and the ePIC detector [6] are also outlined in dedicated documents. Here, the focus will be on
115 the EIC physics case, the synergies with present and planned CERN experiments, and the European involvement
116 in the EIC.

117 The EIC is expected to start operating toward the mid of the 2030’s. It will likely run concurrently with LHC
118 after its high-luminosity upgrade. Hence, it seems appropriate and timely to outline below how investigations at
119 the EIC of each of the above topics could benefit CERN experiments and vice versa.

120 2 The flavor and spin structure of the proton

121 This topic centers around the accurate determination of collinear parton distributions for both unpolarized and
122 polarized protons (and neutrons and deuterons). The unpolarized collinear PDFs currently used for LHC studies
123 have an (NNLO) uncertainty of 2.4% for up quarks at $x = 0.5$ and $Q^2 = 100$ GeV, but 12% for down quarks, 140%
124 for strange quarks and 34% for gluons [7, 8]. The uncertainty quickly rises for all flavors at $x \gtrsim 0.6 - 0.7$ (see
125 Ref. [9]).

126 It is important to constrain PDFs in the limit of large x over a wide range of Q^2 because they influence the
127 production rate of high transverse momentum W and Z bosons and jets, as well as the possible production of new
128 heavier partners that are predicted in several BSM extensions (see the DIS document for more details). LHC data
129 will help to decrease these uncertainties, particularly after the high-luminosity upgrade [10], but for the search for
130 BSM physics at the LHC it is essential that the employed PDFs are obtained from data that are insensitive to
131 that BSM physics. Proposed future experiments at CERN, such as a fixed-target experiment [11] or the LHeC
132 experiment (see the document on DIS submitted to the ESPPU Panel) could provide such data with high precision.
133 An overall 1% uncertainty in the PDFs would be the desired goal at the LHC to confront with theory [7]. High
134 statistics data obtained with the EIC from neutral and charged currents in electroweak DIS will help to reach

135 a better precision at large x , especially for the EIC configuration with maximum center-of-mass energy of 140
 136 GeV. For instance, a projection study shows that charged current DIS at the EIC would have very strong impact
 137 on the $x\bar{d} + x\bar{s}$ combination of quark distributions [9]. Moreover, the EIC will extend these measurements to a
 138 completely new domain with effective neutron targets by using deuterium beam and the capability to tag spectator
 139 protons [12]. This will be a unique dataset to improve the down quark PDF knowledge and test isospin symmetry.

140 The EIC can measure various processes from which the contribution from different quark and antiquark flavors
 141 can be separately extracted over a very broad range in x . These processes include not only neutral and charged
 142 current electroweak DIS but also semi-inclusive DIS (SIDIS), where a hadron in the final state is identified. SIDIS
 143 at the EIC is particularly useful for a precise determination of the strange quark distribution [9]. Such analyses
 144 go hand in hand with the extraction of collinear fragmentation functions (FFs), where light flavor contributions
 145 can be individually tagged. Therefore, our knowledge of PDFs is influenced also by the accuracy at which FFs are
 146 known. The FFs are usually determined in B -factory experiments by measuring electron-positron collisions, but
 147 this yields only a limited knowledge of each individual flavor contribution, and the gluon channel is reachable only
 148 at subleading order. Ideally, one should extract FFs by performing a global fit to data of all available reactions,
 149 including hadron collider data. At present, this was done only by one group [13, 14]. More recently, the NNPDF
 150 collaboration found that hadron collider data (CDF, CMS, ALICE) can significantly constrain the gluon FFs [15].
 151 On the other hand, the (anti)strange FFs still suffer from large uncertainties, and this reflects in a large uncertainty
 152 on the (anti)strange PDFs as well. More generally, the limitations of the current SIDIS data hinder a complete
 153 flavor separation of unfavored channels. At the EIC, the high luminosity, combined with the large lever arm in
 154 the hard scale Q and the purposefully planned detector capabilities, will allow for very precise studies of the flavor
 155 dependence of FFs over a large phase space. Current studies on the projected relative error indicate that significant
 156 improvements can be achieved also for PDFs of light flavors over a wide range of low to medium x , particularly
 157 for the strange component [9]. Hence, combining inputs from the EIC, hadron colliders and B -factories, will allow
 158 to drastically reduce the uncertainties on FFs, and could make it possible also to reach the ultimate goal of a
 159 simultaneous extraction from data of both PDFs and FFs. Additionally, it could help in clarifying if the intrinsic
 160 flavor content of the proton (i.e., Fock components in its wave function) receives contributions also from charm [16].

Figure 2: Integrated gluon helicity as a function of the attainable x_{\min} for various EIC configurations [17].

161 The availability of polarized proton beams at the EIC allows a similar analysis for the polarized quark and
 162 gluon PDFs and thereby the possibility to shed further light on their contribution to the proton spin. In particular,
 163 the strange quark and gluon PDFs still have large uncertainties. Recent results obtained at RHIC give evidence
 164 that the gluon contribution is nonvanishing and positive, although the uncertainty is large because the result is
 165 very sensitive to the minimum attainable x (x_{\min}). With its unique capability of colliding longitudinally polarized
 166 electrons and protons, while spanning small x even below 10^{-4} , the EIC will drastically reduce this uncertainty
 167 (see Fig. 2). Both DIS and SIDIS data will be important here, as well as the development of reliable and versatile
 168 Monte Carlo generators to analyze them. In this field, Europe has a recognized leadership and can give a crucial

169 contribution.

170 **3 Three-dimensional structure of nucleons and nuclei in momentum** 171 **and configuration space**

172 One of the main topics to be studied with the EIC is that of transverse momenta and positions of quarks and
173 gluons inside hadrons, as quantified by TMDs and GPDs, respectively. The ultimate aim of such studies is to
174 gain a deeper insight into the dynamics of quarks and gluons in hadrons than can be inferred from PDFs alone.
175 TMDs and GPDs have been central to the investigations conducted earlier by the HERMES experiment at DESY
176 and currently by the COMPASS experiment at CERN and at Jefferson Lab with both polarized and unpolarized
177 targets. Quark TMDs are typically studied using SIDIS and in jet and vector boson production in proton-proton
178 collisions. Quark GPDs are typically studied through the Deeply Virtual Compton Scattering (DVCS) and Deeply
179 Virtual Meson Production (DVMP) processes. Polarized light ions at the EIC (both longitudinal and transverse)
180 are crucial for fully resolving the diverse spin-spatial and spin-momentum correlations of hadronic structure.

181 **TMD factorization and evolution**

182 Many critically important aspects of TMDs can be studied experimentally with the EIC. Apart from measuring
183 the various TMDs [18] for polarized and unpolarized quarks, gluons and/or hadrons, the TMD formalism itself can
184 be thoroughly investigated.

185 TMD factorization, which allows for the theoretical description of particle spectra at small or intermediate
186 transverse momentum, needs to be tested. A main objective is to demonstrate to what extent the TMDs are
187 universal (like the collinear PDFs and FFs). Although the TMD for unpolarized quarks and hadrons is expected to
188 be the same in SIDIS and Drell-Yan (DY), for some polarized cases there is a calculable process dependence. In 2015
189 and 2018 the COMPASS experiment acquired DY data with the objective of testing this (more specifically, determining
190 the predicted overall sign difference between the SIDIS and DY measurements of the Sivers TMD effect) and the
191 results so far are consistent with the expectations from the TMD formalism, although the uncertainties are still
192 large. The same applies to the asymmetry measurements at RHIC in W production [19]. Furthermore, for gluon
193 TMDs even the unpolarized case is expected to be non-universal [20]. Hence, it is important to compare observables
194 at the EIC with related observables at the LHC, e.g., for quarkonium production [21] or Higgs production [22],
195 where it was shown that the transverse momentum distribution of bosons as heavy as the Higgs particle can
196 be affected by TMDs of gluons with small intrinsic transverse momentum. The specific predictions from TMD
197 formalism can be safely tested in a high Q^2 regime ($Q^2 \gg M_p^2$), in order to avoid complications from power
198 suppressed quark-gluon correlation effects. In addition, TMD evolution, i.e., the Q^2 dependence of the predictions,
199 needs to be tested, as was done extensively for the scaling violations in DIS with HERA, showing that Altarelli-
200 Parisi equations (DGLAP evolution) for collinear PDFs work over many orders of magnitude, but at the same
201 time hinting at possible deviations at small x and moderate Q^2 [23]. Investigation of the latter regime is another
202 objective of the EIC (covered in Sec. 4).

203 **Transition between TMD and collinear frameworks**

204 Besides testing its predictions, the limitations of the TMD formalism also need to be clarified. For this purpose
205 proton-proton collisions, even unpolarized ones, are particularly useful. Currently, it is expected on theoretical
206 grounds that azimuthal correlations in dijet production in $p-p$ collisions do not factorize [24]. The size of the
207 factorization breaking effects is entirely unknown and can only be assessed from a comparison of high energy $p-p$
208 and $e-p$ collisions. The data from HERA on dijet production in $e-p$ collisions is too limited to do this with
209 existing data. Recent studies of various dijet measurements at the EIC indicate that they are feasible [25, 26].
210 The same applies to D -meson pair production, which is another process of interest for TMD factorization breaking
211 tests.

212 The TMD formalism applies to the region of low transverse momenta (much smaller than the large scale in the
213 process). Therefore, sufficient momentum resolution is required in the full p_T range in order to test the limits of
214 applicability and the transition to the collinear formalism that applies at large p_T . In many of the observables of
215 interest, such as azimuthal correlations in the Drell-Yan process (studied by, e.g., CMS [27] and ATLAS [28]), the
216 momentum resolution is currently limited, but that will improve over time. The same applies to di-photon and
217 quarkonium (pair) production. The transition region of intermediate p_T has recently attracted much attention from

218 the theoretical point of view [29, 30]. Because of the additional degrees of freedom (observables differential in more
219 variables) it is harder to reach the same level of precision as for observables calculable in collinear factorization.
220 Nevertheless, at present N³LL expressions are available for a number of processes [31, 32] and more data, from
221 LHC and other experiments, are needed to confront with theoretical predictions.

222 GPDs

223 GPDs enter collinear factorization expressions and are expected to be universal. While the associated theory has
224 reached a high level of sophistication, progress on relevant measurements has been comparatively slow because the
225 experiments require high statistics for exclusive processes and excellent detector coverage. HERA, COMPASS and
226 Jefferson Lab experiments have already obtained experimental information on some of the GPDs, but this is only
227 the beginning when it comes to extractions of the GPDs with precision and in a sufficiently large kinematic domain.
228 The capabilities of the EIC will open the way to a thorough exploration of GPD properties. In particular, the large
229 Q^2 coverage will enable tests of GPD evolution and studies of power-suppressed higher-order correlations.

230 GPDs encode information about the spatial distribution of partons inside a hadron, correlated with their
231 distribution in longitudinal momentum. The spatial distribution is obtained in a rather direct way by Fourier
232 transforming the differential cross section as a function of the Mandelstamm variable, t , in suitable exclusive
233 reactions like DVCS or DVMP. In an indirect manner, this distribution also influences the dynamics of $p-p$ as
234 well as $p-A$ and $A-A$ collisions, namely in the context of multiparton interactions (MPI). In such interactions,
235 several partons in the colliding hadrons take place in independent hard scatters, and the relative transverse distance
236 between the partons is of crucial importance for this mechanism. Information on the spatial distribution of single
237 partons from GPDs provides a quantitative baseline expectation, on top of which one can then attempt to assess
238 correlation effects between different partons. In this sense, MPI and underlying events description will considerably
239 benefit from a fully developed GPD picture.

240 Moreover, GPDs will enable detailed studies of the spatial distribution (tomography) of several interesting
241 observables like charge, pressure, energy and number densities.

242 TMDs and GPDs have been studied extensively. Various computer codes and tools, to a large extent developed by
243 European groups, are available, such as for example:

244 TMDlib and TMDplotter (<https://tmdlib.hepforge.org/doxy/html/index.html/>),

245 NangaParbat (<https://github.com/MapCollaboration/NangaParbat>),

246 Artemide (<https://github.com/VladimirovAlexey/artemide-public>).

247 For GPD model studies also the package PARTONS (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1512.06174>), which is the basis for
248 EpIC [33], a newly developed generator of exclusive processes.

249 There are also proposals for future TMD and GPD studies at CERN. The AMBER experiment at the M2 beam
250 line of the CERN SPS started operation in 2023 [34], planning Drell-Yan measurements with pion and kaon beams.
251 Another initiative that is being put forward is that of a fixed-target program which would allow scattering of an
252 LHC proton or lead beam on a polarized fixed-target. The physics case for such an experiment has been developed
253 over recent years under the name “AFTER@LHC” [11]; a particular proposal for such a fixed-target experiment
254 at LHCb is called “LHC-spin” and is described in a separate document submitted to this Panel [35]. There would
255 of course be ample synergies between such experiments and the EIC as well.

256 4 QCD in nuclei

257 The EIC will be the first collider ever for deeply inelastic scattering with nuclei, opening up a large new phase space
258 in high atomic number A at small x and large Q^2 that has never before been experimentally accessed (see Fig. 1).
259 Electron-ion collisions allow the the study of the internal structure of heavy ions in terms of elementary partonic
260 constituents, quarks and gluons. In addition to a new understanding of QCD in large nuclei being a fundamental
261 topic in itself, it is also complementary to the program of heavy-ion collisions at the LHC and RHIC. Probing
262 the partonic structure of the colliding nuclei by DIS experiments is important for understanding the production
263 of both the matter that then becomes a quark-gluon plasma, and the jets and other hard probes that are used to
264 explore its properties.

265 Nuclear PDFs

At LHC kinematics, one is mostly sensitive to the region of relatively small x , where the nuclear PDFs are very poorly known since they are hardly constrained by any currently existing data. Studies of modifications to the structure of jets as they pass through deconfined QCD matter are becoming very sophisticated and will form an increasingly important part of the nuclear collision program at the LHC when it moves to higher luminosities. These studies will require a reduction of the large uncertainty of nuclear PDFs at small x , and the EIC will have a significant impact here [36]. In particular, one should note that accurate measurements of charm structure functions at the EIC would have an even larger effect than total cross section measurements, also improving the determination of the nuclear gluon PDF at large x (aiding the further study of the EMC effect and of (anti-) shadowing). Semi-inclusive DIS at large x in nuclei also provides a laboratory to study the energy loss of high-energy partons passing through ordinary, confined nuclear matter. Such measurements provide the comparison that is necessary to calibrate and check theoretical approaches to jet energy loss. Last but not least, exclusive and semi-inclusive measurements will give access to the GPDs and TMDs of nuclei, respectively.

278 Saturation phenomena

279 At high collision energies, or equivalently small x , the phase space available for emitting soft gluons is very large. Since every emitted gluon is itself a source of further radiation, a fast growing cascade is created that leads to a strong growth of the gluon distribution. Eventually unitarity is expected to be preserved due to nonlinear interactions, i.e., gluon merging, that starts to play an important role leading to the phenomenon of gluon saturation. Gluon saturation then controls the physics in DIS collisions in the small x limit at moderate Q^2 . The gluons in the same regime are also responsible for the production of deconfined QCD matter – the quark-gluon plasma – in heavy ion collisions, studied at the LHC and in particular by the ALICE collaboration.

286 Since a high atomic number A also increases the gluon density at a given Q^2 , gluon saturation is accessible in DIS experiments at lower energies with nuclei than with protons. The EIC will provide a versatile experimental program to investigate in detail this new regime of QCD. In order to fully understand this regime, it is important to simultaneously measure inclusive and semi-inclusive cross sections, inclusive diffraction (diffractive structure functions) and exclusive reactions, such as vector meson production and diffractive dijets. The EIC is being designed to be a facility that can perform this broad set of measurements that are necessary for a full picture of the gluonic structure of nuclei.

293 The small- x physics at the EIC is complemented by several measurements that are performed in hadron colliders (RHIC and LHC) to probe aspects of the same physics. Inclusive particle production and two-particle correlations in $p-p$ and $p-A$ collisions, especially at forward rapidities, directly probe the small- x gluons in nuclei. At CERN, these forward measurements are performed at LHCb and, especially with future instrumentation upgrades, at CMS and ATLAS. Furthermore, as mentioned, the small- x and high- A program at the EIC is very closely connected to studies of deconfined QCD matter in heavy-ion collisions. The correct interpretation of several aspects of heavy-ion collisions, such as the so-called "ridge", requires data from high-energy electron-ion experiments.

300 Initial conditions for Quark-Gluon Plasma studies

301 One of the most challenging problems in heavy-ion physics is to understand how the gluons and quarks from the colliding nuclei form a thermalized plasma. Data from $A-A$ collisions seems to be well described by models assuming a very quick formation of an equilibrated medium. It is, however, very difficult to get direct experimental access to the earliest stages of a heavy-ion collision, and the theoretical understanding of the thermalization process is still quite incomplete. Here, the picture of the small- x degrees of freedom in the nucleus obtained from electron-ion collisions is crucial, as it provides the starting point – the initial condition – from which one evolves towards a de-confined matter.

308 In recent studies at the LHC, it has become clear that effects usually attributed to collective behavior in $A-A$ collisions, such as elliptic flow and the ridge, are also visible in $p-A$ and $p-p$ collisions. There is currently an intense debate in the field concerning the correct interpretation of these results. They have been explained either in terms of multi-particle correlations already present in the colliding protons or nuclei, or alternatively ones generated by collective interactions if de-confined QCD matter is present. For a resolution of the puzzle posed by these results, a baseline measurement of such initial state correlations in a more tractable collision system is essential. The ideal experiments for this are provided by $e-p$ and $e-A$ collisions.

315 UPCs

316 Besides being a source for many small- x gluons, ultra-relativistic heavy ions also form a source of strong electro-

317 magnetic fields, which can be probed in Ultra-Peripheral Collisions (UPCs) at high energies. This effectively leads
318 to high-energy photon-ion scattering, where partons at small x are probed both in nuclei (in $A - A$ collisions) and
319 protons (in $p - A$ collisions). Since in these collisions the photon is always quasi-real, one does not have the same
320 ability to vary Q^2 as in DIS experiments, but on the other hand the higher collision energy gives access to smaller
321 values of x than available at the EIC. To date, exclusive vector meson production in $\gamma - A$ collisions measured
322 by ALICE [37] have been used to probe nuclear gluons at small x . The possibility to separately perform coher-
323 ent (nucleus stays intact) and incoherent (nucleus breaks up into smaller color neutral fragments) measurements
324 gives an additional handle on probing the nuclear geometry and its fluctuations, which are important features for
325 understanding the initial state of $A - A$ collisions. Exclusive J/ψ and Υ productions in UPCs have been studied
326 at ALICE, LHCb and CMS. The results (e.g., see Refs. [38, 39, 40]) are consistent with HERA measurements of the
327 same process at lower energies, and can be used to constrain the x dependence in different theory calculations.

328 5 Electroweak physics and the search for physics beyond the Standard 329 Model

Figure 3: Figure of merit for muon identification in the ePIC detector as a function of momentum.

330 The several TeV limits on new particles established by the LHC indicate that if new physics exists it would
331 reside at a significantly higher mass than the SM. In the absence of a much higher energy collider the ideal way
332 to search for new physics is through precision measurements. These measurements could detect the impact of new
333 particles as they may provide corrections through high order diagrams. A framework called SMEFT [41] has been
334 established to evaluate such effects and has shown that the EIC can have a unique capability to place constraints
335 on new physics. In particular, the EIC polarization for both electrons and protons or deuterons coupled with its
336 high luminosity constrain Wilson coefficients that are orthogonal to those probed by Drell-Yan semi-leptonic four
337 fermion interactions at the high luminosity LHC. Additionally, LHC constraints are going to be improved through
338 the increase of knowledge of proton distributions functions.

339 A second important constraint on BSM physics that the EIC can provide is in the sector of charged lepton
340 flavor violation (CLFV) [42, 43]. In this case, the relatively clean collider environment provided by high energy
341 DIS scattering could easily disentangle an electron to tau transition. Several measurements have been proposed
342 looking for tau decays in the final state. The kinematically clean 3-pion decay has been most well developed [44].
343 This channel alone has been shown to be competitive with other constraints from other facilities around the world.
344 Recent analyses have shown that although the ePIC detector does not have a dedicated muon detector, it can
345 still differentiate muons from pions with a high degree of confidence (see figure 3). This opens up new avenues of

346 investigation, especially in the tau to single muon decay that has twice as large a branching ratio compared to the
347 3-pion decay.

348 Besides the constraints offered by electron-proton or electron-deuteron collisions, the EIC can provide additional
349 information for BSM physics from electron-nucleus scattering. One such study [45] focuses on coherent production
350 of tau leptons mediated by an Axion-like particle (ALP). Even with conservative estimates the authors have shown
351 that the EIC can put significant constraints on ALPs at or above the GeV scale. Crucially, the analysis depends on
352 detection capabilities not currently covered by the baseline ePIC detector, leading to opportunities for an upgrade
353 or a future second detector to be able to explore this new physics.

354 Finally, the search for new BSM physics relies on the best possible determination of the SM parameters. Among
355 them, the W mass can be precisely extracted also by fitting the transverse mass and momentum distributions of
356 the W decay products in hadronic collisions [46, 47]. The ability of making precise extractions of TMDs at the EIC,
357 including sensitivity of intrinsic transverse momenta to the flavor of partons entering the collision, might lead to a
358 statistically significant impact of this nonperturbative effect on the extracted values of W^\pm masses (see Ref. [48]
359 for an exploratory work), thus influencing also the search for new BSM physics.

360 6 Conclusions

361 In this document for the ESPPU, we have outlined the European involvement in the U.S.-based Electron-Ion
362 Collider (EIC) which recently received approval for CD-3A allowing the Project to start long-lead procurement.
363 More than a quarter of the EIC User Group and of the ePIC experimental collaboration consists of European
364 scientists. This indicates a large European interest in the EIC, in both its science case and its detector and
365 accelerator development. Furthermore, this document reviews the large variety of mutual benefits for CERN
366 and EIC experiments coming from the connections between the scientific questions addressed. We conclude that
367 strengthening the ties between the particle physics community in Europe and the EIC project would be very
368 beneficial to all parties involved and could foster important progress in research at the forefront of collider physics.

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